

THE PROBLEM OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF PERFORMING PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE

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Abstract. *This article is mainly about the need for students studying in pedagogical educational institutions and doing their pedagogical practice to have the ability to communicate in order to fully perform the pedagogical practice processes and the opinions about the effectiveness of this need. is dedicated.*

Keywords: *pedagogical practice, student, pedagogical activity, communication, communication skills, pedagogical process.*

The events of democratization and humanization taking place in modern society have a decisive impact on the life of education as a social institution. Its problems are not only economic and social, but primarily ideological. That is, changes in the educational paradigm are characterized by the revision of the foundations of the formation of the young generation from the point of view of personal direction.

This transition is directly related to the change of the teacher's position as the leading subject of the pedagogical process. In this regard, it is not inappropriate to impose certain rules on a student doing pedagogical practice. It is from his "Translator" teacher's position that when knowledge, abilities and skills are prioritized in the pedagogical process, the student himself becomes a means to achieve the goal. In this place, he achieves the status of "organizing teacher". This is due to the fact that it is designed to create conditions for self-realization of the student's personality within the pedagogical process.

We know that preparation for teaching is unique. This peculiarity is that the new teacher immediately becomes not only a subject teacher, but also a direct organizer of the pedagogical process from the first days of his practical work.

When preparing future teachers to participate in the pedagogical process, it is necessary to take into account its content, methodological, management and socio-psychological aspects. If the first two directions are clearly expressed in the system of professional training of future teachers, the next two are not enough. In the field of pedagogical communication, these aspects of mastering the teacher's skills can be said to be a separate gap as an integrating factor. It was found appropriate to analyze the reasons for this as follows.

The problem of pedagogical communication is not new for today's education. It can be seen from the existence of a number of sources and literature that various aspects of this problem have been studied by many researchers, and scientists. For example, Russian scientists such as V.A. Kan-Kalik, A.N. Leontiev, A.A. Bodalev conducted research on the nature and structure of pedagogical communication.

In recent years, there has been a certain interest in the problem of relations between teachers and students, in the classroom and in the auditorium. And as a result, a number of scientific research works were born. Studies of Russian scientists such as V.P. Bituev, B.V. Jelanova, S.V. Ivanov, D.A. Mishutin, T.G. Papparina, S.V. Sergeeva, V.V. Tarasov, Yu.P. Timofeev are related to this problem. However, authors often prioritize the psychological or moral aspect of pedagogical communication, and it is observed that the role of communication as a factor of managing the pedagogical process in the lesson is not clearly visible.

On the pages of existing pedagogic textbooks today, the important meaningful component of professional training, which implies a detailed study of pedagogical communication in general, and its management aspect in particular, and as a result of this, the students' knowledge of pedagogy, special subjects and special methods in parallel planes (side by side) exists and it can be seen that it does not form a coherent whole. In our opinion, in the training of a future teacher, insufficient attention is paid to the block of information on the problems of pedagogical communication, which is intended to play the role of a connecting link between the above-mentioned pedagogical disciplines is the result. Because it is no secret that the majority of pedagogical knowledge and skills are realized only through communication skills. Pedagogical activity has a communicative character, and communication is its essence.

It is known that the communicative component's role as a separate system builder in pedagogical activity should be sufficiently taken into account in the content of model curricula. Biorq Principles of Pedagogical Systems Management do not provide for the study of pedagogical communication problems, it is not emphasized that attention should be paid to the management of the pedagogical process through them.

Therefore, based on this, there are certain contradictions in the modern educational society. These contradictions are:

- between the requirements for a graduate of a higher educational institution of pedagogy as an organizer of the educational process and the real level of solving this problem in the process of professional training of a future specialist;

- between the communicative character of pedagogical activity, its practical character, and on the other hand, the superiority of the scientific-subject (knowledge-based) approach to the training of future teachers.

In a broader and more understandable way, in the context of professional training of students, such a necessary component of their future activities as pedagogical communication is not fully expressed. Of course, this cannot reduce the effectiveness of the future teacher's professional training as an educator, teacher and organizer of the pedagogical process. Nevertheless, taking into account the existence of various types of pedagogical activity at the current stage, each of them predetermines the specific nature and structure of pedagogical communication due to its uniqueness. And this should be explained and taught to students in time. Today, it can be said that the problem of pedagogical communication of students engaged in pedagogical practice, that is, future teachers, is of great interest to all scientists. It is very specific, first of all, because of the social stratum, which is why a new term appeared in education - "management communication" the term

The aspect of management communication in pedagogical activity has not yet been sufficiently studied, although it is generally accepted that the relationship between the teacher and pupils, students is the main principle that ensures the active interaction of the subjects of the

pedagogical process at. We see the learning problem in the inconsistencies between the modern pedagogical training system, the completeness of its important components, and the requirements and characteristics of its future professional activity. This contradiction is especially sharply manifested in the field of professional understanding and mastering of management communication functions as a factor of quality organization of the pedagogical process. Regarding this problem, it was considered necessary to recommend the following as the author. It is predicted that these recommendations will serve to further develop the communication competence of future teachers participating in pedagogical practice processes.

We assume that training future teachers in the basics of management communication will have a significant impact on the quality of their functions as organizers of the pedagogical process if the following conditions are met:

- organizing a systematic approach to the formation of communicative skills in the process of professional preparation for managerial communication;

- use of the principle of professional guidance as a system-forming factor;

- interaction of the principle of professional orientation with principles such as the principles of humanization and democratization;

- to guide the continuous and comprehensive development of the future teacher-manager.

If, in order to find the right solution to the problem and to implement it, the development of methods for teaching the basics of management communication to students of pedagogical higher educational institutions and the theoretical justification of its content are the goals, and the five-stage tasks are performed in a sequence, of course, the efficiency will increase. It will be as in ngil. These tasks were expressed as follows:

- study of the problem of pedagogical communication as a management factor in the theory and practice of modern schools;

- theoretical justification and practical proof of the necessity and possibilities of improving communicative pedagogical skills as a result of mastering the functions of management communication in the process of preparing future teachers for professional pedagogical activities;

- to reveal the content, structure, functions of management communication, the basics of its organization;

- development of scientific and practical recommendations on preparing students for management communication as a factor that increases the quality of the teacher's professional activity;

- introduction of a program to teach students the basics of management communication.

The methodological basis of the above is the relationship between activity and communication, the most important philosophical principles of a person as a person. It is also interesting that the subject of activities and relations, the role of communication in the process of formation and development of a person, the relation of objective and subjective factors in the development of a person, the doctrine of a person is the highest value.

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